

“I can feel it coming in the *hairs* tonight”: Characterising Mid-Air Haptics on the Hairy Parts of the Skin

Dario Pittera, *Member, IEEE*, Orestis Georgiou, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Abdenaceur Abdouni, *Member, IEEE*, and William Frier, *Member, IEEE*,

Abstract—Ultrasound mid-air haptics has received much attention from both academic and industrial groups, however, such investigations have almost exclusively focused on the tactile stimulation of glabrous (hairless) skin of our hands. Meanwhile, the non-glabrous (hairy) part of the skin covers the largest area of our body, yet remains largely untouched and unexplored by this haptic technology. 1) We study acoustic streaming and the 2) acoustic radiation force associated with a mid-air haptic stimulus. 3) We characterise the perceived strength, temperature, and definition of the stimulus through a user study. 4) Finally, in a second user study we explore the possibility of conveying affective (pleasant) touch. These objective and subjective experiments provide the first deep understanding of how mid-air haptics can affect tactile perception through stimulating the hairy skin. To that end, we discuss how researchers and haptic designers can leverage mid-air haptic technology to vary the perceived touch intensity, temperature, and deliver affective touch.

Index Terms—mid-air haptics, hairy skin, affective touch, acoustic streaming, acoustic radiation force.

I. INTRODUCTION

DURING the past decade mid-air haptic technology has steadily gained traction among haptic solutions [1]. Its popularity has relied on the ability to deliver tactile sensations at a distance and without the need of any wearable or hand-held devices, achieved through the focusing of ultrasound waves to create a high-pressure focus that is then modulated at perceptible frequencies. This technology has successfully been applied in various fields such as automotive [2], pervasive displays [3], Augmented Reality (AR) [4] and Virtual Reality (VR) [5]. In these applications, the mid-air tactile stimuli have mostly targeted the users’ palms and fingertips as a feedback channel in response to user input, e.g., in a control interface [6]. Meanwhile, many meaningful touch interactions take place on other parts of our body, for example, when we receive a friendly caress from our loved ones or an encouraging pat on the back, when we walk outside and feel the gentle breeze when we sense the first drops of rain on our head and limbs.

The sense of touch permeates our whole body, which is also what makes it such an expressive sense. Limiting applications of mid-air haptic technology to the hands and fingertips (also referred to as glabrous skin) thus limits the potential for enhanced expressiveness and can impinge the overall user experience. For instance, the ability to target the hairy skin using mid-air haptics in a controlled and predictable way could be used as an active channel to grab or increase user attention, what could then find direct application in

Fig. 1. The setup shared by the four experiments presented in this paper (refer to Figure 6A of the Supplemental Material for the original images of the setup). An ultrasound array was fixed to the 3D printer arm, allowing it to move along three axes while stimulating different parts of the user’s forearm.

education, automotive, or digital signage sectors. Additionally, exploiting the sense of touch using mid-air haptics, possibly in combination with wearable haptics [7], on various parts of the human body could deepen immersion in AR and VR applications [8]. Finally, by targeting the hairy-skin we could access the affective part of the sense of touch, which plays a key role in social communication and emotional well-being [9].

Despite all these reasons, mid-air haptic stimulation on the hairy part of the skin has yet to be characterised, though its feasibility has been recently shown for the forearm and the face [10], [11]. One reason for this is the intrinsic difference in how tactile information is perceived on hairy skin compared to glabrous skin. On the glabrous skin, tactile stimuli (contact or non-contact) can be described according to their peak force output and modulation over time. These relationships have been studied and characterised in the case of mid-air haptics [12], [10], [13], hence providing valuable guidelines to haptic designers and enabling their controlled integration in useful applications. Meanwhile, tactile stimuli on the hairy skin are generally characterised according to the stimulus peak force, speed of motion and temperature [14], [15], [16]. There is however no systematic study that has explored these quantities

All authors are with Ultraleap Ltd, Bristol, BS2 0EL, UK, e-mail: dario.pittera@gmail.com.

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Fig. 2. The four experiments presented in this paper. (1) We measured the acoustic streaming (AS) (see Sec. II-B). (2) We measured the acoustic radiation force (ARF) (see Sec. II-B). AS and ARF were measured within a volume of 330 cm^3 that encompasses the ultrasonic FP. (3) Based on the results from experiment (1) and (2), we characterised the perception of mid-air haptics on the hairy skin by collecting quantitative measurements regarding the perceived strength, temperature, and spatial definition of the stimulus when the FP was targeted at different proximal distances from the skin. (4) We explored the possibility of perceiving affective touch, i.e., pleasant tactile sensations through mid-air haptics.

in relation to mid-air haptics, hence limiting their integration and full potential for expressive and social mid-air touch in application settings.

To that end, this paper investigates for the first time how ultrasound mid-air haptics can go beyond the palm and fingertips and examines the perceptual space associated with the induced touch sensations on hairy skin. Specifically, through a set of four experiments divided into two sets of objective measurements and two sets of subjective measurements, we characterised the mid-air haptic output and associated perception on the hairy skin (see Figure 2), and validated the following hypotheses:

H1: acoustic streaming and acoustic radiation force have a greater peak value at the ultrasonic focus position, but cover a greater area when measured away from it.

H2: Stimulating a greater area of the skin translates into a stronger percept, even though the peak pressure is lower, as a result of spatial summation at receptors level.

H3: Mid-air haptic technology can convey pleasant touch.

Through these three hypotheses, the paper will also demonstrate how it is possible to increase the perceived tactile strength of mid-air haptics on the hairy skin and influence the perceived temperature of the mid-air tactile stimulus. Thus, our study provides useful guidelines addressed to haptics designers wanting to target and use mid-air haptic technology onto hairy parts of the skin as an active channel for non-functional haptic applications and therefore go beyond simple notifications and feedback usage to discriminating touch between virtual textures [17] or objects [18]. Finally, this paper highlights the necessity to characterise the physical phenomena surrounding the ultrasound mid-air haptic stimuli such as Acoustic Streaming (AS), and acoustic radiation force (ARF) and how they affect the tactile perception.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Mid-air haptics

Since the first proof of concept in 2008 [19], ultrasound-phased arrays have been increasingly used to deliver haptic feedback in mid-air and in a variety of settings [1]. The technology's ability to target and stimulate the user's skin without the need for any wearables or handheld devices and controllers, has propelled mid-air haptics into a variety of

human-computer interaction (HCI) applications: automotive [2], pervasive displays [3], AR [4] and VR [5], in which various benefits can be transduced such as reduced eye-off the road time, improved user experience, and immersion.

To date, in most applications and investigations involving ultrasound mid-air haptics, the high intensity acoustic pressure point responsible for the vibrotactile effect, also referred to as the focal point (FP), has been targeted to the glabrous part of the user's hand. Going beyond a single static tactile FP and to increase its expressiveness, researchers have developed multiple modulation and signal processing techniques that dynamically vary the strength and position of the FP or FPs. Literature refers to these methods as Amplitude Modulation (AM) [20], Lateral Modulation (LM) [10], and Spatiotemporal Modulation (STM) [21]. The research community has investigated the relationship between the parameter space of these modulation techniques and the associated perceptual space. Specifically, these modulation techniques have been employed to render the shape of 2D [22] and 3D objects [18], conduct virtual material properties such as texture and roughness [17], the flow of fluids [23], complimenting art installations [24], accompany short films [25], communicate emotions [26] and even convey the illusion of supernatural phenomena in VR [27] and AR [4]. This is not an exhaustive list of investigations (see [1] for a review), however what transpires is that the parameter space of AM, LM, and STM is very rich and has been exploited by haptics and HCI researchers to design a multitude of applications and experiences. Secondly, it is worth emphasizing that the tactile stimuli has almost always been targeted to specific parts of the palm (i.e., glabrous skin) rather than to the hairy skin (non-glabrous). Exceptions include Gil et al. [11] who showed that a standard size ultrasonic array of 256 transducers could be used to produce mid-air tactile sensations on the face, specifically on the forehead, cheeks, and between the brows. Another exception includes Takahashi et al. [10] who stimulated parts of the forearm using a larger, more powerful, mid-air haptic display comprising of 996 transducers. Both studies solely reported absolute thresholds relating to the different body locations studied. Furthermore, both studies were using modulation techniques developed for the glabrous skin, without taking into account the specificity of the hairy skin. To that end, this paper undertakes a systematic

study of how ultrasonic mid-air haptics can be applied to the hairy skin, and investigate two physical phenomena associated with the mid-air haptic output: the acoustic radiation force (ARF) and the acoustic streaming (AS).

B. Acoustic Radiation Force and Acoustic Streaming

Ultrasonic mid-air haptic displays manipulate the acoustic field in their vicinity to create high pressure fields that induce tactile sensations when interacted with. Specifically, using a phased array of electronically controlled ultrasonic transducers (usually 256 elements or more) one can accurately apply phase delays between elements as to synchronise and focus the wavefronts from each transducer to a desired position in space, here referred to as focal point (FP). Due to the principle of superposition of waves, the acoustic pressure of each ultrasonic wave adds up, making the acoustic pressure at the FP significantly greater than the ambient pressure. With a 256 transducers array, the maximum acoustic pressure is of the order of 163 dB sound pressure level (SPL).

While linear acoustics and the wave equation describes the build up of pressure at the FP, they do not describe the exchange of momentum with an interacting body (e.g., a hand) nor with the propagation medium (e.g., air). For that, one needs to study, at least from a mathematical point of view, the governing NavierStokes equations that fully describe fluid dynamics. Perturbation analysis can be used to elicit first (linear) and second (nonlinear) or potentially higher order terms of the NavierStokes equations. These are usually quite small, however in the case of mid-air haptics that amalgamate pressures of e.g., 163 dB SPL, second order terms do not time-average to zero and thus become significant, giving rise to the ARF (wave momentum being transferred to the object) causing an indentation on the skin, and AS (wave momentum being transferred to the air) causing a steady air-flow [28].

The ARF can be measured on a precision scale [29], [30] or estimated through numerical analysis [31]. Using a typical 256 transducers array, the ARF produced is of the order of 1 gram force. The exact values will depend on different parameters such as FP position in space, FP SPL, and modulation techniques. The ARF causes a skin displacement of the order of the micrometres, as shown through vibrometry experiments and FEM simulations on glabrous skin [32].

The AS effect can be measured using an anemometer [33] or estimated through numerical analysis [31]. With a typical 256 transducers array, Norasikin et al. measured an airflow up to 0.8 m/s [33]. Note here that the authors were using a different algorithm than a focus algorithm, which means it is unclear what is the AS at the vicinity of an FP. The AS produced with ultrasonic phased array has been used for controlling airflow in various HCI applications, ranging from steering scented air for olfactory transportation and display [34], steering cold air [35], and manipulating fog-displays [33].

C. The hairy skin

The skin is the largest organ of the human body. Functionally and anatomically, we can outline two groups: the glabrous skin and the hairy skin [36]. While both the ARF and the AS

effects can influence our sense of touch on the glabrous skin, it is unclear what their role and importance is on inducing tactile sensations on the hairy skin.

The glabrous skin is devoid of hairs and covers mainly the palmar region of the hand and plantar region of the feet. It is thicker and more densely populated by mechanoreceptors. Its main function is to decode subtle tactile information, e.g., vibrations, friction, pressure, etc., coming from the external world. For instance, it informs us about how much grip we need to hold an object, or if we scratched a surface, what coin we are taking out from our wallet, what is the wallet's texture, etc. The glabrous skin is the most sensitive part of our skin, having lower tactile thresholds and higher spatial acuity [37], [38].

The hairy skin covers more than 90% of our body [39] and presents many important physiological and functional differences compared to the glabrous skin. While we can find almost the same receptors present in the glabrous skin, their density is lower. This means that although the hairy skin maintains discriminative touch capabilities, its spatial acuity is lower, hence, less adapt for this scope [36]. The hairy skin is also innervated by hair units and field units, rapidly adapting receptors with large fields and numerous high-sensitivity spots which are very sensitive to hairs movement [40], [14]. A unique characteristic of the hairy skin sees the presence of special unmyelinated low-threshold mechanoreceptive afferents with low conduction speed (0.5-2 m/s) named C-tactile (CT) fibres [41]. CT fibres seem to respond optimally to continuous strokes (caress-like) in a range of speed between 1 and 10 cm/s, with a preference around 3 cm/s depending on the body location [9], [42]. Their function has been linked to the social and affective part of touch which are key factors towards normal brain development as well as for healthy emotional and cognitive maturation [43]. CT fibres have a poor spatial and temporal resolution, hence they are not suited for discriminative touch [44]. Interestingly, the information arising from these fibres follow alternative pathways to the central nervous system. In contrast with other afferent signals for discriminative touch, information from the CT fibres seems to reach the insula (an area of the brain linked to emotional processing) instead of the primary somatosensory cortex (S1) [41]. Finally, it has been shown that CT fibres have a higher firing rate for stimuli at skin temperature, reinforcing the theory of an affective touch purpose [15].

As mentioned earlier, mid-air haptic applications have mainly focused on glabrous skin stimulation. There might be several factors responsible for that. In the first instance, the hairy skin has been primarily investigated on non-primate species. The hairy skin also holds less tactile discriminative ability which is functionally more important for day-to-day operations and handling. Moreover, the functions of the CT fibres have only been hypothesised recently [9], and are not yet fully understood. Finally, investigating the hairy skin might be more complex as receptive field properties of afferents innervating the arm differ from those of afferents innervating the dorsum of the hand or the face [14]. Together, the considerations discussed above highlight the opportunities of a systematic investigation of the hairy skin.

Fig. 3. A: Setup used to measure AS (refer to Figure 6B of the Supplemental Material for the original images of the setup). The array was moved along the three axes in order to record the generated airflow using an anemometer which remained fixed at (0, 0, 0). B: heat map showing AS speed measurements for the cross-sectional layer at $z = 0$. C: AS measured at $z = 10$ cm. AS is maximal at the FP position (i.e., $x, y, z = 0$) and appears more diffused around the central axis at $z = 10$ cm. Additional measurements are available in the Supplemental material, Section 1 and 2.

III. COMMON EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS

Four experiments were conducted using a common apparatus and setup. We used a 16x16 ultrasonic transducer array, namely the Ultraleap Stratos Explore development kit. The array was fixed to a 3D printer arm, namely the Rostock Max V2, to allow us to precisely move the device along the X, Y, and Z-axes through a serial communication. The array was facing downwards as shown in Figure 1. Opposite to the array, there was a hot-wired anemometer (experiment 1), a precision scale (experiment 2), the participants' volar or dorsal forearm (experiment 3), and the participants' volar forearm or dorsum of the hand (experiment 4). During the two user studies (i.e., experiment 3 and 4), the 3D printer's arm was covered to keep the participants oblivious of the array position in Z and, therefore, to avoid any bias. Finally, the participants wore in-ear headphones with single-use earbuds, playing pink noise to control for the printer, device, and any other environmental noises. Additionally, participants were requested to wear a set of 3M PELTOR X5A earmuffs, rated for 31 dB reduction of audible sound.

IV. EXPERIMENT 1 - ACOUSTIC STREAMING

In this first set of measurements, we recorded the spatial variation of the AS effect within a cuboid region of dimensions 13.2x5x5 encompassing the FP location. This created a 3D grid of data points that record the average airflow speed and can be put together to plot a 3D spatial distribution of the airflow speeds near an FP. Due to symmetry, the cuboid sample region only needed to measure one quadrant of the space. Analysing this distribution is interesting as it can account for a stronger (or weaker) haptic sensation that is perceivable at and nearby the FP. For instance, the hair afferents could be stimulated in a greater or lesser degree depending on the spatial distribution of AS giving rise to a stronger (or weaker) percept.

A. Procedure

We used the setup described in Section III with a hot-wired anemometer (Testo 405i) capable of recording airflow speeds

at a temporal resolution of two seconds. We used the variables illustrated in Figure 4 and the apparatus shown in Figure 3A. The z values are to be interpreted relative to the position of the FP. The FP was rendered at a height of 20 cm from the centre of the ultrasound phased array. Therefore, $z = 0$ cm means we were measuring AS using the anemometer at the FP, while $z = -0.6$ cm means we were measuring AS at 0.6 cm upwind of the FP position.

To allow enough time for the anemometer to record the max peak of the AS for each x, y, z sample location, the array was activated for 16 seconds producing a static FP. Next, we programmed a ten seconds pause to allow the anemometer to reset after turning off the ultrasonic phased array. There were no other external sources of airflow, e.g., open windows.

Fig. 4. Experimental design for Experiment 1 - acoustic streaming. The array was moved to 324 combination of x, y, z locations. Numbers are relative to the FP position.

B. Results

The data collected by the hot-wire anemometer corresponded to a group of values distributed in time over the 16 seconds when the mid-air haptic device was turned on, for each sample point within the cuboid region tested. Hence, we removed the extreme values corresponding to the ramp-up and down of the signal and calculated the mean value for each location tested.

Overall, we observed that the airflow was maximal at the centre of the FP, i.e., at $(x, y, z) = (0, 0, 0)$ reaching 2.9 m/s speed, rapidly dropping to 0.3 - 0.5 m/s in its immediate

Fig. 5. A: setup used to measure ARF (refer to Figure 6C of the Supplemental Material for the original images of the setup). The array was moved along the three axes. The precision scale remained fixed at $(x, y, z) = (0, 0, 0)$. B: heat map showing ARF measurements for the layer at $z = 0$. C: ARF measured at $z = 10$ cm. The ARF is maximal at the FP position (i.e., $x, y, z = 0$), but appears to weaken and spread out around the FP at $z = 10$ cm. Additional measurements are available in the Supplemental material, Section 1 and 3.

vicinity. The AS effect is seen to persist even at $z = 10$ cm downwind of the FP position, with a maximum intensity of 1.5 m/s at the central axis. Importantly, we observe that AS has been distributed over a larger area, a sort of diffuse effect (see Figure 3B,C). While we anticipated the observed results to be symmetric along the $y = x$ axis, a small variation is observed. We attribute this to statistical noise or sensor measurement uncertainty.

At negative z values, i.e., upwind of the FP, the AS speeds were significantly lower with the peak at $(x, y, z) = (0, 0, -1.6)$ and $(0, 0, -3.2)$ being close to 0.5 m/s and dropping rapidly to 0 nearby. Thus, we can imagine that AS has a rapid and concentrated build-up at the FP, and then diffuses in the downwind direction. Any perceivable tactile effect due to AS should therefore follow such a pattern.

V. EXPERIMENT 2 - ACOUSTIC RADIATION FORCE

Similar to the AS experiment, in this second set of measurements we recorded the ARF generated within a volume of space near the FP centre.

A. Procedure

To record the ARF, we used the same apparatus as in Sec. IV with the only difference being the use of a precision scale (KERN PCB 2500-2, 0.01 gr precision) instead of the hot-wired anemometer. The precision scale has a 130 mm x 130 mm plate size, however, to avoid recording the background pressure, we centred the FP onto a 21 mm diameter pillar (enough to cover the area of the mid-air haptic FP), that was placed on the precision scale plate and set this arrangement as the coordinate origin. Moreover, around the pillar, we placed a reflector to keep background acoustic radiation pressure from influencing our measurement.

We used the variables illustrated in Figure 6) and the apparatus shown in Figure 5A. Using the 3D printer, the array was moved to different locations relative to the pillar and scale. Once the array reached the desired location, it was turned on for seven seconds to allow the precision scale to reach a

stable measurement, which was recorded. After turning the array off, we programmed a pause of ten seconds to be sure the precision scale was zeroed. Data from the precision scale were recorded through a serial port, together with the relative (x, y, z) coordinates of the array.

Fig. 6. Experimental design for Experiment 2 - acoustic radiation force. The array was moved in 324 combination of x, y, z locations and measurements were repeated three times. Numbers are relative to the FP.

B. Results

The data collected by the precision scale were averaged at each location tested. Overall, the results obtained exhibit similar trends than the results from Sec. IV on AS. Namely, we observed that ARF was maximal at the FP position (i.e., at $0, 0, 0$) recording about 1 gram of force (gf), rapidly dropping to 0.05 gf at $(2, 0, 0)$. The ARF effects recorded at $(0, 0, 10)$, i.e., downwind of the FP position had a maximum intensity of 0.19 gf at the central axis but were also distributed over a larger area (see Figure 5B,C), for instance, at $(0, 2, 0)$ ARF = 0.05 gf vs 0.12 gf at $(0, 2, 10)$, or at $(2, 2, 0)$ ARF = < 0.01 gf vs 0.08 gf at $(2, 2, 10)$.

As with the previous experiment, negative z values recorded a much weaker ARF than at the FP or in the downwind direction. This second set of measurements confirms the previous results. Our hypothesis is that mid-air haptic stimuli targeting locations positively offset to the FP might be perceived as stronger due to spatial summation effect at the receptors' level. To verify this, we carried on a user studies presented in the next sections.

VI. PRELIMINARY DISCUSSION

The reported two sets of measurements were aimed at verifying $H1$, and overall we can say that the data from the hot-wire anemometer and the precision scale are in agreement with $H1$. Namely, we observed that AS and ARF are maximal at the FP and diffuse and spread out in the downwind direction (refer to Section 5 of the Supplemental material for information on the FP size.). However, it is not known what will be the perceptive consequence of these phenomena. In $H2$ we hypothesised that stimulating a greater area of the skin will translate into a stronger percept, as a result of spatial summation at receptors level.

VII. EXPERIMENT 3 - MID-AIR HAPTICS ON HAIRY SKIN

The two previous experiments indicated that AS and ARF effects become sparser in the downwind direction of the FP. In this experiment, we investigated if these effects influence a participant's perceived haptic strength of the FP. Further, when we deliver an ultrasonic mid-air stimulus we generate acoustic streaming, that presents as a stream of air. This stream of air becomes greater as we increase the distance between the focal point and the skin (as demonstrated in Experiment 2). Having an air flow above a warm surface accelerates the temperature exchange between the surface and the air. Hence, we had reason to believe that the sensation could have been perceived as colder, therefore, we investigated also the perceived temperature. Finally, we also explored the perceived spatial definition of the FP (i.e., the sharpness of the FP).

A. Participants

A total of 25 participants took part in this study (6 females, age $\mu = 31.3$, $SD \pm 4.4$). They had normal or glasses/lens corrected vision and no history of neurological or psychological disorders. All participants were right-handed. Upon arrival, participants were asked to read the information sheet and sign a consent form before the task was explained to them.

B. Procedure

We exploited an STM mid-air haptic stimulus slowly moving along a liner path. Specifically the stimulus was moving symmetrically passing through the mid-point of the volar (palm facing upwards towards the array) or dorsal (palm facing downwards) part of the forearm at a constant speed of 8 cm/s along a 10 cm line. The speed of 8 cm/s was chosen so to keep the stimulus duration close to 1 second. A very short internal pilot study confirmed that this stimulus speed was perceivable. We choose those locations on the arm as they are both covered by hairy skin and are easily accessible. The line haptic sensation was delivered only once, while the FP moved from proximal to distal direction along the 10 cm line. Finally, our 3D printer setup allowed us to move the array in the z direction thus enabling us to study what the STM haptic sensation at 20 cm from the array felt like when at a z offset of 0, 0.6, 1.6, 3.2, 5.8, and 10 cm downwind of the sensation focus. Negative offsets were briefly investigated

in a pilot study with five participants that reported a non-perceivable stimulus.

The testing phase started by delivering the reference stimulus at a $z = 1.6$ cm offset. A 2.5 sec time window was allowed during which the array was moved up or down by the 3D printer. Then, the comparison stimulus was delivered. At the beginning of each stimulus (i.e., reference and comparison), the participants could hear a 0.5 s "beep" sound from their earphones to focus their attention, and immediately after, feel the haptic stimulus. The z value for the comparison stimulus was chosen at random from the six previously listed. Therefore, the array could move up or down with respect to the reference stimulus position. The height adjustment speed was adapted so that it would always take 2.5 seconds to reach the desired height, thus removing any possible user bias from printer motion duration estimation. The experiment was repeated for both volar and dorsal areas of the forearm. In between each pair of stimuli, a 10-sec pause would follow to avoid habituation. Each pair of stimuli was repeated three times per location for a total of 18 pairs of stimuli delivered on the volar forearm, and 18 on the dorsal forearm.

At the end of each trial, participants were required to use the mouse to rate the comparison stimulus with respect to the reference one along three dimensions: perceived strength, temperature, and spatial definition. To do that they had to move three sliders, one for each dimension investigated, ranging from -3 to +3, where -3 meant weaker/colder/sparser than the reference stimulus, +3 stronger/warmer/sharper than the reference stimulus, and 0 meant equal to the reference stimulus. If needed, the participants could repeat the pair of stimuli by clicking on a specific button on the user interface. Before the testing phase, participants were given three trials (different from the testing phase) to build confidence with the procedure while the researcher running the study ensured participants understood the procedure before commencing the experimental phase.

We next report on the results of our user study relating to the three dimensions studied (i.e., perceived strength, temperature, and definition) for the different z height offsets and parts of the forearm (i.e., volar and dorsal).

C. Results - Dorsal Forearm

Perceived strength: The data showed that the larger the distance between the skin and the FP, the greater is the perceived strength of the stimulation. For our dataset, a quadratic fit obtained an $R^2 = 0.92$ (Figure 7, left). To investigate differences between perceived strength at different distances from the dorsal forearm, we explored the data distribution with a Shapiro-Wilk test. Data followed a normal-like distribution ($p = 0.13$). Therefore, we applied a One-Way Repeated Measures ANOVA. The ANOVA test highlighted significant differences in the rating scores of our sample, $F(5, 144) = 36.43$, $p < 0.001$. To further investigate the differences between groups, we carried on a Tukey's Test for post-hoc analysis. All comparisons were statistically different apart from the pairs of 0 vs 0.6, 1.6 vs 3.2, 3.2 vs 5.8, and 5.8 vs 10 cm. Perceived strength ratings increase with increasing positive z distance offset from the haptic sensation centre.

Fig. 7. Left: quadratic fit of data relative to the perceived strength of a FP at different distances from participants dorsal forearm. Right: linear fit of perceived temperature on the dorsal forearm.

Fig. 8. Left: Quadratic fit of data relative to the perceived strength of a FP at different height distances from the participants volar forearm. Right: Linear fit of perceived temperature on the volar forearm.

Perceived temperature: The data on the perceived temperature followed a clear negative linear trend. The greater the distance from the FP, the lower the perceived temperature. The linear fit showed a R^2 of 0.99 (see Figure 7, right). After a Shapiro-Wilk test, we found that our variable was deviating from a normal distribution ($p < 0.001$). A Friedman test highlighted statistically significant differences in perceived temperature at different distances, $\chi^2(5) = 72.168, p < 0.001$. Wilcoxon signed-rank test found all the comparisons between groups to be significantly different with the only exception of 0 vs 0.6 cm.

Perceived spatial definition: results of the perceived definition of the haptic line sensation are less conclusive. Data showed a poor fit to a quadratic model ($R^2 = 0.21$) and to a linear regression ($R^2 = 0.2$). In both cases, the distance variable resulted non-statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, we cannot conclude that the distance from the FP was influencing the perceived definition of the haptic stimulus.

Correlations between variables: we explored the correlations between the variables measured on the dorsal forearm.

We found a strong negative significant correlation between perceived strength and perceived temperature ($r = -0.64$). That is, stimuli perceived as stronger were also perceived as colder. We also found a low negative significant correlation between perceived strength and definition ($r = -0.21$); the stimuli perceived as stronger were also perceived as more sparse on the hairy skin.

D. Results - Volar Forearm

Perceived strength: As for data on the dorsal forearm, data on the volar forearm seemed to fit well a quadratic model with a $R^2 = 0.96$ (Figure 8, left). We analysed the perceived strength data on the volar forearm by using the same procedure applied to dorsal forearm data. Data followed a normal-like distribution ($p = 0.2$). The One-Way Repeated Measures ANOVA test highlighted significant differences in the rating scores of our sample, $F(5, 144) = 41.44, p < 0.001$. From a Tukey's Test for post-hoc analysis, all comparisons were statistically different apart from 0 vs 0.6, 3.2 vs 5.8, 3.2 vs 10, and 5.8 vs 10 cm.

Perceived temperature: our data could fit a quadratic model, $R^2 = 0.93$ (Figure 8, right). After a Shapiro-Wilk test, we found that our variable was deviating from a normal distribution ($p < 0.001$). A Friedman test highlighted statistically significant differences in perceived temperature at different distances, $\chi^2(5) = 63.59, p < 0.001$. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test between groups found comparisons to be statistically different except for 0 vs 0.6, 0.6 vs 1.6, and 1.6 vs 3.2 cm.

Perceived spatial definition: data on the perceived definition at the volar forearm seemed to align with a quadratic trend ($R^2 = 0.69$) better than data on the dorsal forearm. Also, in this case we did not find any statistically significant difference when comparing the different distances from the haptic stimulus centre ($\chi^2(5) = 10.30, p = 0.06$).

Correlations between variables: we explored the correlations between the variables measured on the volar forearm. We found a moderate negative significant correlation between perceived strength and perceived temperature ($r = -0.43$). We also found a low negative significant correlation between perceived strength and definition ($r = -0.29$). This time, we detected also a low positive significant correlation between perceived temperature and perceived definition ($r = 0.14$). That is, the colder a stimulus was perceived, the more spread out it felt.

E. Results - Differences between Dorsal and Volar Forearm

Interested in investigating whether there were differences between the results at the dorsal and volar part of the forearm, we directly compared the three variables discussed above. Depending on the distribution of our variables we used a paired t-test or a Wilcoxon test. None of the comparisons led to any statistically significant difference (all p -values were greater than 0.05). Hence, we can conclude that the participants' perception of the stimuli provided on the two parts of the forearm tested were comparable.

VIII. EXPERIMENT 4 - AFFECTIVE TOUCH IN MID-AIR

As discussed in Sec. II-C, one of the peculiarities of the hairy skin is its ability to decode affective touch characteristics. In particular, the hairy skin is populated by C-tactile fibres that when stimulated at speeds between 1 and 10 cm/s (with an optimal speed of ~ 3 cm/s [9], [42]), convey pleasant tactile sensations. Therefore, in this second user study, we aimed to investigate *H3*, i.e., if slow-paced mid-air haptic stimulations can elicit a more pleasant sensation in comparison with out-of-range stimuli (i.e., $>$ or $<$ 1-10 cm/s).

As mid-air haptic stimulation do not have a broad resolution in terms of intensity, we also accounted for the possibility that stronger stimuli will be also perceived as more pleasant by collecting participants' perceived strength of the stimuli.

A. Participants

A total of 17 participants took part in the study (4 females, age $\mu = 31.5$, $SD \pm 5.3$). They had normal or glasses/lens corrected vision and no history of neurological or psychological disorders. All participants were right-handed. Upon arrival, participants received the information sheet and signed a consent form before the task explanation.

B. Procedure

We used the same apparatus as in the previous user study with the array producing a FP at 20 cm below its centre and the user's arm positioned a further 3 cm away from the array (23 in total) so that the stimulus was perceivable but not too cold (based on results from Sec. VII-D). Indeed, previous research demonstrated that affective touch is optimal at skin temperature [15]. As there were no differences between the volar and dorsal part of the forearm (see Sec VII-E), we focused only on the volar forearm and we added another target location on the dorsum of the hand, still part of the hairy skin but presenting different afferents' receptive field properties [14]. Similarly to experiment 3, we exploited an STM moving haptic stimulus. Specifically the FP was moving along a linear path of 10 cm length along the volar forearm, and 5 cm along the dorsum of the hand. The location order was counterbalanced across participants.

The stimuli were moving at six different speeds: 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20 cm/s. Each stimulus was presented randomised and repeated three times. To avoid habituation, we inserted a 10-sec pause between each stimulation. The stimulus was moving in a proximal to distal direction. While mid-air tactile stimulation cannot be seen, participants were instructed to look on a fixation point on the screen to avoid unwanted expectations to bias their answers. Participants wore earphones playing pink noise to control for device and environmental noises. As for experiment 3, a 0.5 s "beep" sound was played before delivering the haptic stimulus.

Participants rated the perceived pleasantness of the stimuli presented on a scale from -10 to 10 (Unpleasant - Pleasant) and strength (on a scale from 1 to 7, Weak - Strong) of the stimulus just felt.

C. Results - Dorsum of the hand

Before analysing the influence of the stimulus' speed on the perceived pleasantness, we checked our dependent variable

Fig. 9. Box plot of pleasantness ratings at different stimulus' speeds tested on the dorsum of the hand. In green, we highlighted speed = 20cm/s; this was the only speed to differ significantly from speeds = 0.5, 2.5, and 10 cm/s.

Fig. 10. Quadratic fit for pleasantness ratings tested on the dorsum of the hand at different stimuli’ speeds.

(i.e., pleasantness ratings) for normality. A Shapiro-Wilk test confirmed the visual inspection ($p = 0.25$).

Figure 9 shows the averages calculated on the pleasantness ratings for the different stimuli speeds presented. It is known that CT receptors exhibit a quadratic behaviour with respect to speeds [45], [9], [42]. Therefore, we fit data into a quadratic model to investigate further possible differences between the ratings, obtaining a $R^2 = 0.94$ as shown in Figure 10. While the fit is strong, we note that more data is required for us to argue towards the existence of an optimal stimulus speed.

Our model and the results from an ANOVA repeated measures indicated statistically significant differences between the different speeds considered, $F(1, 100) = 8.14, p = 0.005$. A Tukeys Test highlighted differences ($p \leq 0.05$) between the 20 cm/s speed and the 0.5, 2, 5, and 10 cm/s speeds. This data trend is noticeable in Figure 9.

Further, we investigated the correlations between perceived pleasantness and perceived strength at different stimuli’ speeds. We found a significant, moderate correlation ($r = 0.53$) between the ratings of pleasantness and the perceived strength. We also detected small negative correlations between the stimulus speed and the perceived pleasantness ($r = -0.27$), and between speed and perceived strength ($r = -0.24$) that reached significance level.

D. Results - Volar forearm

Finally, we analysed data on the forearm using a similar procedure and statistical tests to those on the dorsum of the hand. The data followed a normal-like distribution, Shapiro-Wilk test ($p = 0.2$). Figure 11 shows the average measured pleasantness ratings for the different stimuli speeds presented. Again, it seems that the perceived pleasantness for stimuli at different speed did not vary greatly. We proceeded by fitting data to a quadratic model to investigate possible differences between the ratings ($R^2 = 0.52$). Indeed, our model indicated no statistical differences between the different stimuli speeds on the volar forearm. The correlations between perceived pleasantness and perceived strength, at different stimulus speeds, showed a moderate and significant correlation ($r = 0.51$).

IX. DISCUSSION

This paper describes four experiments, two objective and two subjective, aimed to study and characterise the effect of mid-air haptics onto hairy parts of the skin.

Through experiments 1 and 2, we established that at the FP centre, the AS and ARF are maximal and tightly focused. Downwind of the FP, the AS and ARF tend to diffuse, decay, and spread out smoothly. This is particularly true for AS, which remains strong and noticeable even at 10 cm away from the FP position, unlike the ARF that decays much faster. The diffuse spreading of AS and ARF over a larger cross-sectional area downwind of the FP ($z > 0$) confirms *H1*.

[46] describe AS as a laminar (non-turbulent) flow phenomenon. However, after an impact with a solid surface (e.g., the human body), AS will turn into turbulence. Hence, it might be that the perceived sensation could be inflated by vibrotactile effects due to vortexes shedding. The hairy skin has a very low sensitivity for discriminative touch, including vibrations, because of the low Pacinian density in the hairy skin. As a matter of fact, mid-air haptic stimulation on the forearm was only recently reported to be possible by using LM/STM techniques, which generate a high SPL unmodulated focal point directly onto the forearm and rapidly moved it on the skin surface to produce vibrotactile effect [10]. These facts together led us to hypothesise that the AS and ARF tactile effect will be perceived as stronger since they are spread over a larger skin area *H2*, leveraging a spatial summation phenomenon at receptors level, although we cannot completely exclude the vibrotactile effects arising from a turbulent streaming. Experiment 3 confirmed *H2* providing a way to modulate the perceived strength and temperature of a mid-air haptic stimulation on the hairy skin.

In the mean results showed in Figure 7 and 8, we can observe that ratings for stimuli equal to the reference are not exactly at zero. This is expected in psychophysical studies and probably due to statistical power (relatively small sample), and the complexity of the sensitive tactile stimulus and apparatus. Nevertheless, the fact that at 1.6 cm, the result is almost 0, in

Fig. 11. Box plot of pleasantness ratings at different stimuli’ speeds tested on the volar forearm.

a range of ± 3 is as expected.

Results on the perceived spatial definition are less clear, as one would expect given the non-discriminative capabilities of hairy skin [47]. The data we have collected indicated that participants felt the stimulation at the FP as the most dispersed. That is, even when the FP was positioned exactly on the skin, participants did not feel a particularly localised point. This is counter-intuitive since objective measurements of experiments 1 and 2 identified that both the ARF and the AS at the FP were highly localized within a central 1 cm^2 area. However, it is possible that participants did not feel the stimulus at all and decided to rate it as more disperse.

No significant difference was observed from our data between volar and dorsal parts of the forearm. One may argue that the number of hairs on the dorsal forearm is generally higher than the volar forearm, hence, the dorsal forearm should be more sensitive to tactile stimulation. Although the volar part of the forearm present visibly less hairs than its counterpart on the dorsal side, both locations should have the same sensitivity. In [48], the authors demonstrated how, for instance, the hair follicle density between men and women, even if they appear different at the naked eye, are null. Further, they also state that depilation did not affect tactile perception.

Experiment 4 aimed at validating $H3$ relating to the ability to convey pleasant touch through mid-air haptics. Our results shows that on the dorsum of the hand, the highest speed (i.e., 20 cm/s) was felt as less pleasant in comparison to the slower speeds.

As expected, a moderate correlation between perceived strength and pleasantness was observed. Given however that the mid-air haptic device employed in our experiments has a limited dynamic range, it is possible that this observation is not generalisable and that in our case pleasantness was correlated with perceivability and not strength. A pre-test has highlighted that speeds well below or above the experimental range of $1\text{-}20 \text{ cm/s}$, were not perceivable and thus not pleasant.

A. Mid-air haptics design implications

The results reported from the set of experiments discussed within this paper can help researchers and designers in HCI in several ways.

Through experiments 1 and 2 we have identified that while ARF and AS coexist and are two closely coupled physical phenomena generated by ultrasound mid-air haptics, they differ significantly in their spatial signatures. While these phenomena cannot be produced separately in most practical application settings, for the first time, we systematically characterised AS and ARF attenuation and how that is perceived by the participants as a tactile effect on the hairy skin under the form of perceived strength and perceived temperature. This might benefit the design of mid-air tactile sensations. We illustrated how AS is more diffuse than ARF which is mostly concentrated near the focal point. This difference in spatial signatures can be used by haptic designers to create distinct tactile effects. Specifically, vibrotactile effects can be produced through ARF and LM/STM for a focal point positioned on the hairy skin at $z=0$. The perceived strength of a stimulus

targeting the hairy skin can be increased by exploiting AS at different distances from the skin. That is, we showed that pressure based stimulation due to ARF is not the main contributor, but rather that the dominant effect is due to the large skin area stimulated. In a similar way, temperature variations can be produced through AS (i.e., cooling effect) with a focal point positioned at different distances from the skin. Finally, we set the first step towards the generation of pleasant sensations using mid-air haptics on the hairy skin at $z = 3 \text{ cm}$ in the range of $1\text{-}10 \text{ cm/s}$.

B. Limitations and future works

First, the setup used throughout the experiments only allowed for a limited z movement. This means that we could test a FP delivered at 20 cm from the array centre and at a maximum distance of 10 cm from the measurement point or the participants' arm. Although our data fit well a quadratic model in experiments 3 and 4, it is not clear if further distances from the FP would result in a stronger or weaker percept.

In experiment 3, we did not randomise the order of presentation of the reference and comparison stimulus. One might think that participants expected the comparison stimulus to be stronger or weaker than the reference. On the other hand, we chose our reference stimulus to be close to what we had expected to be the median value. Indeed, our data revealed that participants were correctly scoring the stimuli as lower or higher in comparison to the reference stimulus, independently of the presentation order.

In Experiments 3 and 4, our participant sample was not gender-balanced. As previously discussed, in [48], the authors demonstrated how there are no difference in the hair follicle density between men and women. On the contrary, women were found to have a higher density due to different body size. Finally, they also state that depilation did not affected tactile perception. Therefore, there might be no main differences inter-gender, although we cannot exclude it, as most of the participants tested were males.

When considering the conclusions and initial findings presented in experiment 4, one should appreciate that social and affective touch are complex and deep notions with many other characteristics playing key roles. For instance, perceived touch pleasantness changes depending on the gender [49], [50], the relationship between people [51], the compliance of the object being touched [52], cultural differences [53], to name a few. The dimensions studied within this paper are simpler than that, and can only account for robot-human interactions involving mid-air touch. However, we claim that our observations are a first and necessary step towards enabling future computer systems that can intelligently create and enhance our tactile experiences that were previously lost in the virtual transition.

Finally, our experiments focused on the forearm. It is unclear if our results generalise to other hairy body parts. AS and ARF values are likely to be influenced by the shape and mechanical properties of a body part, and such effect could already be present in our experiments because of the different boundary conditions (e.g., free field vs flat reflector). Additional work would be required to characterise such variables.

X. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied two physical phenomena associated with mid-air haptics as generated by an ultrasound phased array: acoustic streaming and acoustic radiation force. We showed that airflow and force are most concentrated at the high-pressure focal point centre generated by the array and that they decay and diffuse in the array downwind direction. Following on from these results, we performed an initial characterisation of the perceived mid-air haptic effects on the hairy skin (forearm) and confirmed that a focal point is perceived as stronger and colder when the targeted 10 cm away from it. While the acoustic radiation force at 10 cm downwind from the focus drops significantly (5x), airflow drops less rapidly (2x) and spreads out to cover a larger area. Thus, we conjecture that a spatial summation effect takes place at the receptors' level resulting in the observed tactile phenomenon. The cooling sensation is probably a direct by-product of the airflow onto the skin (evaporative cooling) [54]. After successfully stimulating the hairy skin in mid-air, we further explored the possibility of delivering affective touch. Initial results seem to confirm that this was possible and that a stronger tactile sensation was correlated with a pleasant one.

Our research helps by providing guidelines for the use of mid-air haptics on the hairy parts of the skin while also demonstrating the largely unexplored area of mid-air affective touch. Applications of this untethered haptic technology can thus extend way beyond functional haptics (notifications and haptic feedback) and can well have a positive impact on the way we interact with machines and with each other in real, virtual, and synthetic spaces.

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Dario Pittera received his B.S. in Communication and Psychology (2011) and his M.S. in Clinical psychology, developmental psychology and neuropsychology (2014), both from the Universit degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy. He worked as a researcher at the Policlinico di Milano Hospital (2013/2014) and at the University of Birmingham from (2015/2016), investigating haptic technology through psychophysical experiments. He then worked as a Lab Associate at Disney Research, Pittsburgh, PA, US as a part of his PhD degree, received in 2019 at the University of Sussex working on mid-air haptics illusions and embodiment. Currently, he is working as a haptics research engineer at Ultraleap. His research is focused on the perception and exploration of mid-air haptic technology.

and the 2019 IEEE Heinrich Hertz Award.

Orestis Georgiou received a PhD in mathematics from the University of Bristol (2011). After a post-doc at the Max Planck Institute for Complex Physics, he joined Toshiba Telecommunications Research Laboratory (2013) as a Senior Engineer and worked on mathematical models of large scale complex wireless networks. Orestis then joined Ultraleap as Academic Program Manager and later as Research Director - his current role. He is an author of over 80 papers, 5 patents, and is the recipient of two best paper awards, a Marie Curie individual fellowship,

and the 2019 IEEE Heinrich Hertz Award.

Abdenaceur Abdouni received his PhD degree in Biophysics engineering from the central school of Lyon, at the beginning of 2018. Before joining Ultraleap, he worked at Laboratory of Tribology and Dynamics systems as a Post Doc. Then he joined Ultraleap as Senior Haptics Researcher. Abdenaceur is an author of more than 15 journal papers. His research interests include haptics, biophysics, skin, tribology, modelling, and topography.

Pierre and Marie Curie (France), making him a key person in the development and integration of modular ultrasound mid-air haptic devices for industrial and robotic applications.

William Frier William Frier has a PhD Human-Computer Interaction and is the Lead Haptics Researcher at Ultraleap. He has been working with Ultraleap technology for more than 5 years and has published and patented extensively on the foundational aspects of mid-air haptics. William has been a key investigator in studying the perception of mid-air haptics which lead to various publications in HCI and Haptic conferences. He has studied Electrical and Electronical engineering at ESIGELEC (France) and Intelligent System and Robotics at University